

Striped Magic Squares of Even Orders 4, 6, 8 and 10

*The work is also available as pdf file at author's sites:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=10587>*

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Abstract

*This work brings **striped** magic squares of even orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 based on **equal width magic rectangles**. These are of type 2×4 , 2×6 , 2×8 , etc. Magic squares constructed based on **equal width magic rectangles**, we call as **striped magic squares**. In case of order 4, we have only one examples. In case of order 6 there are two examples. In case of order 8, there total 9 examples. Finally, in case of order 10 there are 115 **striped magic squares**. The complete list is given at author's web-site. Link is given above. In some cases, the rotational forms of magic squares are also given.*

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Contents

1 Introduction	3
2 Striped Magic Squares of Order 4	3
3 Striped Magic Squares of Order 6	4
3.1 Rotational Striped Magic Squares of Order 6	4
4 Striped Magic Squares of Order 8	7
4.1 Rotational Striped Magic Squares of Order 8	8
5 Striped Magic Squares of Order 10	12
5.1 Rotational Striped Magic Squares of Order 10	16
6 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers	33

1 Introduction

Let's understand first about **striped magic rectangles**, i.e., **equal width magic rectangles**. These are of orders 2×4 , 2×4 , 2×4 , etc. Below are examples of some equal width stripes. The only difference is in length:

66	33	67	36	202						
35	68	34	65	202						
101	101	101	101							
53	45	52	51	47	55	303				
48	56	49	50	54	46	303				
101	101	101	101	101	101					
19	78	99	96	10	73	13	16	404		
82	23	2	5	91	28	88	85	404		
101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101		
43	59	48	51	45	57	54	52	41	55	505
58	42	53	50	56	44	47	49	60	46	505
101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101

The above stripes are used for the striped magic squares of order 10. The striped magic squares of order 4, 6, 8 and 10 are also based on these stripes. The only difference is that their magic rectangles sums are different. Extra examples of rotational forms of magic squares of order 6, 8 and 10 are also given. These are calculated based on script by H. White [1].

2 Striped Magic Squares of Order 4

Below is an examples of **striped magic square** of order 4

	mgc			34	
	15	2	14	3	34
	8	9	5	12	34
	1	16	4	13	34
	10	7	11	6	34
4x4	34	34	34	34	34

There is only way to write rotation of above magic square, i.e., only its transpose.

3 Striped Magic Squares of Order 6

Below are two examples of **striped magic squares** of order 6

1	mgc							111
	11	26	6	31	3	34	111	
	28	9	29	8	36	1	111	
	10	27	32	5	2	35	111	
	25	12	7	30	33	4	111	
	21	13	20	19	15	23	111	
	16	24	17	18	22	14	111	
6x6	111	111	111	111	111	111	111	

2	mgc							111
	11	28	10	25	3	34	111	
	26	9	27	12	36	1	111	
	6	29	32	7	2	35	111	
	31	8	5	30	33	4	111	
	21	13	20	19	15	23	111	
	16	24	17	18	22	14	111	
6x6	111	111	111	111	111	111	111	

3.1 Rotational Striped Magic Squares of Order 6

Both the above magic squares of order 6 presents different forms of rotational striples magic squares. In case first example we have four possibilities, and in case of second example we have eight possibilities.

Example 3.1. Below are four **rotational forms** of first **striped** magic squares of order 6

1	mgc							111
	11	26	6	31	3	34	111	
	28	9	29	8	36	1	111	
	10	27	32	5	2	35	111	
	25	12	7	30	33	4	111	
	21	13	20	19	15	23	111	
	16	24	17	18	22	14	111	
6x6	111	111	111	111	111	111	111	

1	mgc							111
	14	22	18	17	24	16	111	
	23	15	19	20	13	21	111	
	4	33	30	7	12	25	111	
	35	2	5	32	27	10	111	
	1	36	8	29	9	28	111	
	34	3	31	6	26	11	111	
6x6	111	111	111	111	111	111	111	

1	mgc							111
	16	21	25	10	28	11	111	
	24	13	12	27	9	26	111	
	17	20	7	32	29	6	111	
	18	19	30	5	8	31	111	
	22	15	33	2	36	3	111	
	14	23	4	35	1	34	111	
6x6	111	111	111	111	111	111	111	

1	mgc							111
	34	1	35	4	23	14	111	
	3	36	2	33	15	22	111	
	31	8	5	30	19	18	111	
	6	29	32	7	20	17	111	
	26	9	27	12	13	24	111	
	11	28	10	25	21	16	111	
6x6	111	111	111	111	111	111	111	

Example 3.2. Below are eight *rotational forms* of first *striped* magic squares of order 6

2	mgc							111
	11	28	10	25	3	34	111	
	26	9	27	12	36	1	111	
	6	29	32	7	2	35	111	
	31	8	5	30	33	4	111	
	21	13	20	19	15	23	111	
	16	24	17	18	22	14	111	
6x6	111	111	111	111	111	111	111	

2	mgc							111
	34	3	25	10	28	11	111	
	1	36	12	27	9	26	111	
	35	2	7	32	29	6	111	
	4	33	30	5	8	31	111	
	23	15	19	20	13	21	111	
	14	22	18	17	24	16	111	
6x6	111	111	111	111	111	111	111	

2	mgc							111
	14	22	18	17	24	16	111	
	23	15	19	20	13	21	111	
	4	33	30	5	8	31	111	
	35	2	7	32	29	6	111	
	1	36	12	27	9	26	111	
	34	3	25	10	28	11	111	
6x6	111	111	111	111	111	111	111	

2	mgc							111
	16	24	17	18	22	14	111	
	21	13	20	19	15	23	111	
	31	8	5	30	33	4	111	
	6	29	32	7	2	35	111	
	26	9	27	12	36	1	111	
	11	28	10	25	3	34	111	
6x6	111	111	111	111	111	111	111	

2	mgc							111
	16	21	31	6	26	11	111	
	24	13	8	29	9	28	111	
	17	20	5	32	27	10	111	
	18	19	30	7	12	25	111	
	22	15	33	2	36	3	111	
	14	23	4	35	1	34	111	
6x6	111	111	111	111	111	111	111	

2	mgc							111
	11	26	6	31	21	16	111	
	28	9	29	8	13	24	111	
	10	27	32	5	20	17	111	
	25	12	7	30	19	18	111	
	3	36	2	33	15	22	111	
	34	1	35	4	23	14	111	
6x6	111	111	111	111	111	111	111	

2	mgc							111
	14	23	4	35	1	34	111	
	22	15	33	2	36	3	111	
	18	19	30	7	12	25	111	
	17	20	5	32	27	10	111	
	24	13	8	29	9	28	111	
	16	21	31	6	26	11	111	
6x6	111	111	111	111	111	111	111	

2	mgc							111
	34	1	35	4	23	14	111	
	3	36	2	33	15	22	111	
	25	12	7	30	19	18	111	
	10	27	32	5	20	17	111	
	28	9	29	8	13	24	111	
	11	26	6	31	21	16	111	
6x6	111	111	111	111	111	111	111	

In this way we have total 12 **striped** magic squares of order 6.

4 Striped Magic Squares of Order 8

Below are 9 examples of **striped magic squares** of order 8.

1	mgc		260		
	12 54 55 9	8 58 59 5	260		
	53 11 10 56	57 7 6 60	260		
	1 63 62 4	13 51 50 16	260		
	64 2 3 61	52 14 15 49	260		
	25 39 38 28	24 42 43 21	260		
	40 26 27 37	41 23 22 44	260		
	20 46 47 17	29 35 34 32	260		
	45 19 18 48	36 30 31 33	260		
8x8	260 260 260 260	260 260 260 260	260		
2	mgc		260		
	12 54 55 9	8 57 13 52	260		
	53 11 10 56	58 7 51 14	260		
	1 63 62 4	59 6 50 15	260		
	64 2 3 61	5 60 16 49	260		
	25 40	20 45	24 42 43 21	260	
	39 26	46 19	41 23 22 44	260	
	38 27	47 18	29 35 34 32	260	
	28 37	17 48	36 30 31 33	260	
8x8	260 260 260 260	260 260 260 260	260		
3	mgc		260		
	1 64	11 54	17 48	25 40	260
	3 62	55 10	45 20	39 26	260
	63 2	9 56	22 43	34 31	260
	61 4	16 49	44 21	37 28	260
	60 5	52 13	42 23	32 33	260
	58 7	14 51	24 41	30 35	260
	6 59	50 15	47 18	27 38	260
	8 57	53 12	19 46	36 29	260
8x8	260 260 260 260	260 260 260 260	260		
4	mgc		260		
	8 1 63 61	60 58 6 3	260		
	57 64 2 4	5 7 59 62	260		
	17 48	25 40	29 36	21 44	260
	20 45	39 26	35 30	24 41	260
	47 18	38 27	34 31	43 22	260
	46 19	28 37	32 33	42 23	260
	9 16	11 52	53 14	55 50	260
	56 49	54 13	12 51	10 15	260
8x8	260 260 260 260	260 260 260 260	260		
5	mgc		260		
	8 57	17 20 47 46	9 56	260	
	1 64	48 45 18 19	16 49	260	
	63 2	25 40	29 36	11 54	260
	61 4	39 26	35 30	52 13	260
	60 5	38 27	34 31	53 12	260
	58 7	28 37	32 33	14 51	260
	6 59	21 24 43 42	55 10	260	
	3 62	44 41 22 23	50 15	260	
8x8	260 260 260 260	260 260 260 260	260		
6	mgc		260		
	12 57 56 4	2 64	46 19	260	
	53 8 9 61	63 1	59 6	260	
	14 51	39 25 38 28	47 18	260	
	50 15	26 40 27 37	5 60	260	
	48 17	34 32 29 35	16 49	260	
	62 3	31 33 36 30	22 43	260	
	11 54	45 52 24 23	44 7	260	
	10 55	20 13 41 42	21 58	260	
8x8	260 260 260 260	260 260 260 260	260		
7	mgc		260		
	59 8 47 12	50 19	45 20	260	
	6 57 18 53	15 46	9 56	260	
	10 55	43 24 42 21	16 49	260	
	17 48	22 41 23 44	60 5	260	
	52 13	3 64 7 63	54 4	260	
	51 14	62 1 58 2	11 61	260	
	36 32 27 37	34 30 25 39	260		
	29 33 38 28	31 35 40 26	260		
8x8	260 260 260 260	260 260 260 260	260		
8	mgc		260		
	22 43	13 52	20 45	12 53	260
	44 21	51 14	46 19	54 11	260
	23 42	50 15	47 18	55 10	260
	41 24	16 49	17 48	9 56	260
	3 1 63 61	60 58 6 8	260		
	62 64 2 4	5 7 59 57	260		
	37 27 32 36	34 30 25 39	260		
	28 38 33 29	31 35 40 26	260		
8x8	260 260 260 260	260 260 260 260	260		
9	mgc		260		
	22 44 23 41	20 45	12 53	260	
	43 21 42 24	46 19	54 11	260	
	13 51 50 16	47 18	55 10	260	
	52 14 15 49	17 48	9 56	260	
	3 1 63 61	60 58 6 8	260		
	62 64 2 4	5 7 59 57	260		
	37 27 32 36	34 30 25 39	260		
	28 38 33 29	31 35 40 26	260		
8x8	260 260 260 260	260 260 260 260	260		

4.1 Rotational Striped Magic Squares of Order 8

Above there are nine **striped** magic squares of order 8. The last three allows us to different **rotational forms**. See below these examples.

Example 4.1. Below are four **rotational forms of striped** magic squares of order 8 given in Example 7

7	mgc							260	
	59	8	47	12	50	19	45	20	260
	6	57	18	53	15	46	9	56	260
	10	55	43	24	42	21	16	49	260
	17	48	22	41	23	44	60	5	260
	52	13	3	64	7	63	54	4	260
	51	14	62	1	58	2	11	61	260
	36	32	27	37	34	30	25	39	260
	29	33	38	28	31	35	40	26	260
8x8	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

7	mgc							260	
	26	40	35	31	28	38	33	29	260
	39	25	30	34	37	27	32	36	260
	61	11	2	58	1	62	14	51	260
	4	54	63	7	64	3	13	52	260
	5	60	44	23	41	22	48	17	260
	49	16	21	42	24	43	55	10	260
	56	9	46	15	53	18	57	6	260
	20	45	19	50	12	47	8	59	260
8x8	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

7	mgc							260	
	29	36	51	52	17	10	6	59	260
	33	32	14	13	48	55	57	8	260
	38	27	62	3	22	43	18	47	260
	28	37	1	64	41	24	53	12	260
	31	34	58	7	23	42	15	50	260
	35	30	2	63	44	21	46	19	260
	40	25	11	54	60	16	9	45	260
	26	39	61	4	5	49	56	20	260
8x8	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

7	mgc							260	
	20	56	49	5	4	61	39	26	260
	45	9	16	60	54	11	25	40	260
	19	46	21	44	63	2	30	35	260
	50	15	42	23	7	58	34	31	260
	12	53	24	41	64	1	37	28	260
	47	18	43	22	3	62	27	38	260
	8	57	55	48	13	14	32	33	260
	59	6	10	17	52	51	36	29	260
8x8	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

Example 4.2. Below are four **rotational forms of striped** magic squares of order 8 given in Example 8

8	mgc									260
		22	43	13	52	20	45	12	53	260
		44	21	51	14	46	19	54	11	260
		23	42	50	15	47	18	55	10	260
		41	24	16	49	17	48	9	56	260
		3	1	63	61	60	58	6	8	260
		62	64	2	4	5	7	59	57	260
		37	27	32	36	34	30	25	39	260
		28	38	33	29	31	35	40	26	260
8x8		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

8	mgc									260
		26	40	35	31	29	33	38	28	260
		39	25	30	34	36	32	27	37	260
		57	59	7	5	4	2	64	62	260
		8	6	58	60	61	63	1	3	260
		56	9	48	17	49	16	24	41	260
		10	55	18	47	15	50	42	23	260
		11	54	19	46	14	51	21	44	260
		53	12	45	20	52	13	43	22	260
8x8		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

8	mgc									260
		28	37	62	3	41	23	44	22	260
		38	27	64	1	24	42	21	43	260
		33	32	2	63	16	50	51	13	260
		29	36	4	61	49	15	14	52	260
		31	34	5	60	17	47	46	20	260
		35	30	7	58	48	18	19	45	260
		40	25	59	6	9	55	54	12	260
		26	39	57	8	56	10	11	53	260
8x8		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

8	mgc									260
		53	11	10	56	8	57	39	26	260
		12	54	55	9	6	59	25	40	260
		45	19	18	48	58	7	30	35	260
		20	46	47	17	60	5	34	31	260
		52	14	15	49	61	4	36	29	260
		13	51	50	16	63	2	32	33	260
		43	21	42	24	1	64	27	38	260
		22	44	23	41	3	62	37	28	260
8x8		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

Example 4.3. Below are eight *rotational forms of striped* magic squares of order 8 given in Example 8

9	mgc									260
		22	44	23	41	20	45	12	53	260
		43	21	42	24	46	19	54	11	260
		13	51	50	16	47	18	55	10	260
		52	14	15	49	17	48	9	56	260
		3	1	63	61	60	58	6	8	260
		62	64	2	4	5	7	59	57	260
		37	27	32	36	34	30	25	39	260
		28	38	33	29	31	35	40	26	260
8x8		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

9	mgc									260
		53	12	45	20	41	23	44	22	260
		11	54	19	46	24	42	21	43	260
		10	55	18	47	16	50	51	13	260
		56	9	48	17	49	15	14	52	260
		8	6	58	60	61	63	1	3	260
		57	59	7	5	4	2	64	62	260
		39	25	30	34	36	32	27	37	260
		26	40	35	31	29	33	38	28	260
8x8		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

9	mgc									260
		28	38	33	29	31	35	40	26	260
		37	27	32	36	34	30	25	39	260
		62	64	2	4	5	7	59	57	260
		3	1	63	61	60	58	6	8	260
		52	14	15	49	17	48	9	56	260
		13	51	50	16	47	18	55	10	260
		43	21	42	24	46	19	54	11	260
		22	44	23	41	20	45	12	53	260
8x8		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

9	mgc									260
		26	40	35	31	29	33	38	28	260
		39	25	30	34	36	32	27	37	260
		57	59	7	5	4	2	64	62	260
		8	6	58	60	61	63	1	3	260
		56	9	48	17	49	15	14	52	260
		10	55	18	47	16	50	51	13	260
		11	54	19	46	24	42	21	43	260
		53	12	45	20	41	23	44	22	260
8x8		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

9	mgc							260	
	28	37	62	3	52	13	43	22	260
	38	27	64	1	14	51	21	44	260
	33	32	2	63	15	50	42	23	260
	29	36	4	61	49	16	24	41	260
	31	34	5	60	17	47	46	20	260
	35	30	7	58	48	18	19	45	260
	40	25	59	6	9	55	54	12	260
	26	39	57	8	56	10	11	53	260
8x8	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

9	mgc							260	
	22	43	13	52	3	62	37	28	260
	44	21	51	14	1	64	27	38	260
	23	42	50	15	63	2	32	33	260
	41	24	16	49	61	4	36	29	260
	20	46	47	17	60	5	34	31	260
	45	19	18	48	58	7	30	35	260
	12	54	55	9	6	59	25	40	260
	53	11	10	56	8	57	39	26	260
8x8	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

9	mgc							260	
	26	39	57	8	56	10	11	53	260
	40	25	59	6	9	55	54	12	260
	35	30	7	58	48	18	19	45	260
	31	34	5	60	17	47	46	20	260
	29	36	4	61	49	16	24	41	260
	33	32	2	63	15	50	42	23	260
	38	27	64	1	14	51	21	44	260
	28	37	62	3	52	13	43	22	260
8x8	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

9	mgc							260	
	53	11	10	56	8	57	39	26	260
	12	54	55	9	6	59	25	40	260
	45	19	18	48	58	7	30	35	260
	20	46	47	17	60	5	34	31	260
	41	24	16	49	61	4	36	29	260
	23	42	50	15	63	2	32	33	260
	44	21	51	14	1	64	27	38	260
	22	43	13	52	3	62	37	28	260
8x8	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

Combining all the **rotational forms** we have total 22 **striped** magic squares of order 8.

5 Striped Magic Squares of Order 10

Below are few examples of **striped magic squares** of order 10.

1	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
3	1	99	97	96	6	94	8	9	92	505
98	100	2	4	5	95	7	93	11	90	505
25	76	43	58	38	63	35	66	91	10	505
75	26	60	41	61	40	68	33	89	12	505
27	74	42	59	64	37	34	67	88	13	505
73	28	57	44	39	62	65	36	14	87	505
72	29	53	45	52	51	47	55	86	15	505
70	31	48	56	49	50	54	46	16	85	505
32	69	17	83	19	81	24	22	78	80	505
30	71	84	18	82	20	77	79	23	21	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

3	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
3	1	99	97	96	6	94	8	9	92	505
98	100	2	4	5	95	7	93	11	90	505
25	76	48	53	57	42	60	43	91	10	505
75	26	56	45	44	59	41	58	89	12	505
27	74	49	52	39	64	61	38	88	13	505
73	28	50	51	62	37	40	63	14	87	505
72	29	54	47	65	34	68	35	86	15	505
70	31	46	55	36	67	33	66	16	85	505
32	69	17	83	19	81	24	22	78	80	505
30	71	84	18	82	20	77	79	23	21	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

8	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
3	1	99	97	96	6	94	8	9	92	505
98	100	2	4	5	95	7	93	11	90	505
25	76	48	56	49	50	54	46	91	10	505
75	26	53	45	52	51	47	55	89	12	505
27	74	63	40	37	62	65	36	88	13	505
73	28	38	61	64	39	34	67	14	87	505
72	29	58	41	59	44	68	33	86	15	505
70	31	43	60	42	57	35	66	16	85	505
32	69	17	83	19	81	24	22	78	80	505
30	71	84	18	82	20	77	79	23	21	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

17	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
96	21	72	13	20	18	74	91	93	7	505
5	80	29	88	81	83	27	10	8	94	505
85	16	43	60	42	57	35	66	82	19	505
4	97	58	41	59	44	68	33	1	100	505
30	71	38	61	64	39	34	67	25	76	505
6	95	63	40	37	62	65	36	92	9	505
79	22	53	45	52	51	47	55	28	73	505
99	2	48	56	49	50	54	46	75	26	505
3	89	17	24	78	87	70	32	15	90	505
98	12	84	77	23	14	31	69	86	11	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

22	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
96	21	72	13	20	18	74	91	93	7	505
5	80	29	88	81	83	27	10	8	94	505
85	16	46	55	36	67	33	66	82	19	505
4	97	54	47	65	34	68	35	1	100	505
30	71	50	51	62	39	44	57	25	76	505
6	95	49	52	37	64	59	42	92	9	505
79	22	56	45	40	61	41	60	28	73	505
99	2	48	53	63	38	58	43	75	26	505
3	89	17	24	78	87	70	32	15	90	505
98	12	84	77	23	14	31	69	86	11	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

25	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
13	88	93	8	68	33	69	23	38	72	505
18	83	95	6	40	61	32	78	63	29	505
85	16	5	96	30	71	54	47	22	79	505
87	14	7	94	44	57	48	53	58	43	505
84	17	90	11	80	21	49	52	59	42	505
20	81	10	91	34	67	46	55	74	27	505
82	19	92	9	73	28	56	45	60	41	505
15	86	12	89	35	66	50	51	36	65	505
1	99	98	4	77	62	37	26	25	76	505
100	2	3	97	24	39	64	75	70	31	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

29	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
13	88	93	8	45	55	47	51	52	53	505
87	14	92	9	56	46	54	50	49	48	505
15	86	12	89	21	80	29	71	70	32	505
85	16	7	94	79	22	72	30	31	69	505
84	17	90	11	74	27	37	63	62	40	505
18	83	10	91	23	78	64	38	39	61	505
82	19	95	6	77	24	36	65	41	60	505
20	81	5	96	26	75	33	68	58	43	505
1	99	4	98	76	25	67	34	59	42	505
100	2	97	3	28	73	66	35	44	57	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

33	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
13	88	93	8	53	52	47	51	45	55	505
87	14	92	9	48	49	54	50	56	46	505
15	86	10	91	70	71	29	32	23	78	505
85	16	5	96	31	30	72	69	21	80	505
84	17	90	11	62	40	63	37	76	25	505
18	83	12	89	39	61	38	64	79	22	505
82	19	95	6	41	60	67	34	77	24	505
20	81	7	94	58	43	66	35	26	75	505
1	98	4	99	59	42	36	65	74	27	505
100	3	97	2	44	57	33	68	28	73	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

37	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
13	88	93	8	52	55	47	51	45	53	505
87	14	92	9	49	46	54	50	56	48	505
15	86	12	89	23	78	36	65	41	60	505
85	16	7	94	79	22	67	34	58	43	505
84	17	95	6	74	27	33	68	59	42	505
18	83	5	96	21	80	66	35	44	57	505
82	19	90	11	77	24	37	63	62	40	505
20	81	10	91	26	75	64	38	39	61	505
4	98	1	99	76	25	70	32	71	29	505
97	3	100	2	28	73	31	69	30	72	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

41	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
1	98	4	99	45	55	47	52	51	53	505
100	3	97	2	56	46	54	49	50	48	505
13	88	93	8	41	60	36	65	76	25	505
87	14	92	9	58	43	33	68	28	73	505
15	86	10	91	59	42	67	34	74	27	505
85	16	7	94	44	57	66	35	23	78	505
84	17	12	89	37	62	63	40	77	24	505
18	83	90	11	64	39	38	61	26	75	505
82	19	95	6	29	71	70	32	79	22	505
20	81	5	96	72	30	31	69	21	80	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

45	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
21	79	28	77	26	74	76	23	55	46	505
80	22	73	24	75	27	25	78	45	56	505
66	36	33	67	37	64	32	69	47	54	505
35	65	68	34	63	38	70	31	51	50	505
59	58	44	41	62	29	39	72	53	48	505
42	43	57	60	40	71	61	30	52	49	505
1	100	5	96	9	92	13	88	82	19	505
4	97	8	93	91	10	16	85	17	84	505
98	3	94	7	90	11	86	15	83	18	505
99	2	95	6	12	89	87	14	20	81	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

49	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
45	56	41	58	59	44	62	39	71	30	505
55	46	60	43	42	57	40	61	70	31	505
47	54	33	67	36	66	63	38	29	72	505
51	50	68	34	65	35	37	64	32	69	505
52	49	21	74	79	23	77	26	76	28	505
53	48	80	27	22	78	24	75	25	73	505
98	3	8	93	9	92	13	88	17	84	505
99	2	94	7	91	10	87	14	83	18	505
4	97	5	96	90	11	86	15	82	19	505
1	100	95	6	12	89	16	85	20	81	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

53	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
48	53	63	38	58	43	78	23	71	30	505
56	45	40	61	41	60	24	77	70	31	505
49	52	37	64	59	42	79	22	29	72	505
50	51	62	39	44	57	21	80	32	69	505
54	47	65	34	68	35	25	75	74	28	505
46	55	36	67	33	66	76	26	27	73	505
1	100	7	5	12	10	95	93	92	90	505
99	2	94	96	89	91	6	8	9	11	505
4	97	13	87	82	85	84	15	18	20	505
98	3	88	14	19	16	17	86	83	81	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

55	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
98	4	99	1	46	54	50	49	56	48	505
3	97	2	100	55	47	51	52	45	53	505
88	13	94	7	36	65	62	37	40	63	505
14	87	96	5	67	34	39	64	61	38	505
19	82	89	12	33	68	44	59	41	58	505
16	85	91	10	66	35	57	42	60	43	505
17	84	6	95	76	25	21	79	24	78	505
86	15	8	93	26	75	80	22	77	23	505
83	18	9	92	27	74	32	29	70	71	505
81	20	11	90	73	28	69	72	31	30	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

57	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
18	85	13	15	87	20	82	84	1	100	505
83	16	88	86	14	81	19	17	4	97	505
5	95	93	7	92	12	90	10	98	3	505
96	6	8	94	9	89	11	91	99	2	505
21	80	73	32	27	75	25	30	70	72	505
24	77	28	69	74	26	76	71	31	29	505
78	23	35	62	38	65	64	33	67	40	505
79	22	66	39	63	36	37	68	34	61	505
57	59	52	48	51	55	54	41	43	45	505
44	42	49	53	50	46	47	60	58	56	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

58	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
44	57	79	78	24	21	96	5	83	18	505
42	59	22	23	77	80	6	95	16	85	505
49	52	66	35	28	73	8	93	88	13	505
53	48	39	62	69	32	94	7	86	15	505
50	51	63	38	74	27	9	92	14	87	505
46	55	36	65	26	75	89	12	81	20	505
47	54	37	64	76	25	11	90	19	82	505
60	41	68	33	71	30	91	10	17	84	505
58	43	34	67	31	70	99	98	4	1	505
56	45	61	40	29	72	2	3	97	100	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

62	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
4	97	94	7	48	53	21	80	25	76	505
98	3	8	93	59	42	79	22	75	26	505
1	100	95	6	43	58	78	23	74	27	505
99	2	5	96	51	50	24	77	28	73	505
13	87	86	16	57	44	33	67	66	36	505
88	14	15	85	41	60	68	34	35	65	505
17	84	9	92	54	47	32	69	62	39	505
83	18	91	10	55	46	70	31	40	61	505
82	19	90	11	52	49	29	72	63	38	505
20	81	12	89	45	56	71	30	37	64	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

64	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
23	61	36	38	76	69	27	74	55	46	505
78	40	65	63	25	32	66	35	45	56	505
75	26	57	43	60	42	79	22	52	49	505
34	67	44	58	41	59	30	71	51	50	505
72	29	31	77	62	28	37	68	47	54	505
21	80	70	24	39	73	64	33	53	48	505
1	100	7	5	12	10	90	93	92	95	505
98	3	94	96	89	91	11	8	9	6	505
4	97	18	87	82	85	84	15	13	20	505
99	2	83	14	19	16	17	86	88	81	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

41	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505	45	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505	49	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505																
1	98	4	99	45	55	47	52	51	53	505	21	79	28	77	26	74	76	23	55	46	505	45	56	41	58	59	44	62	39	71	30	505	
100	3	97	2	56	46	54	49	50	48	505	80	22	73	24	75	27	25	78	45	56	505	55	46	60	43	42	57	40	61	70	31	505	
13	88	93	8	41	60	36	65	76	25	505	66	36	33	67	37	64	32	69	47	54	505	47	54	33	67	36	66	63	38	29	72	505	
87	14	92	9	58	43	33	68	28	73	505	35	65	68	34	63	38	70	31	51	50	505	51	50	68	34	65	35	37	64	32	69	505	
15	86	10	91	59	42	67	34	74	27	505	59	58	44	41	62	29	39	72	53	48	505	52	49	21	74	79	23	77	26	76	28	505	
85	16	7	94	44	57	66	35	23	78	505	42	43	57	60	40	71	61	30	52	49	505	53	48	80	27	22	78	24	75	25	73	505	
84	17	12	89	37	62	63	40	77	24	505	1	100	5	96	9	92	13	88	82	19	505	98	3	8	93	9	92	13	88	17	84	505	
18	83	90	11	64	39	38	61	26	75	505	4	97	8	93	91	10	16	85	17	84	505	99	2	94	7	91	10	87	14	83	18	505	
82	19	95	6	29	71	70	32	79	22	505	98	3	94	7	90	11	86	15	83	18	505	4	97	5	96	90	11	86	15	82	19	505	
20	81	5	96	72	30	31	69	21	80	505	99	2	95	6	12	89	87	14	20	81	505	1	100	95	6	12	89	16	85	20	81	505	
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

53	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505	55	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505	57	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505																
48	53	63	38	58	43	78	23	71	30	505	98	4	99	1	46	54	50	49	56	48	505	18	85	13	15	87	20	82	84	1	100	505	
56	45	40	61	41	60	24	77	70	31	505	3	97	2	100	55	47	51	52	45	53	505	83	16	88	86	14	81	19	17	4	97	505	
49	52	37	64	59	42	79	22	29	72	505	88	13	94	7	36	65	62	37	40	63	505	5	95	93	7	92	12	90	10	98	3	505	
50	51	62	39	44	57	21	80	32	69	505	14	87	96	5	67	34	39	64	61	38	505	96	6	8	94	9	89	11	91	99	2	505	
54	47	65	34	68	35	25	75	74	28	505	19	82	89	12	33	68	44	59	41	58	505	21	80	73	32	27	75	25	30	70	72	505	
46	55	36	67	33	66	76	26	27	73	505	16	85	91	10	66	35	57	42	60	43	505	24	77	28	69	74	26	76	71	31	29	505	
1	100	7	5	12	10	95	93	92	90	505	17	84	6	95	76	25	21	79	24	78	505	78	23	35	62	38	65	64	33	67	40	505	
99	2	94	96	89	91	6	8	9	11	505	86	15	8	93	26	75	80	22	77	23	505	79	22	66	39	63	36	37	68	34	61	505	
4	97	13	87	82	85	84	15	18	20	505	83	18	9	92	27	74	32	29	70	71	505	57	59	52	48	51	55	54	41	43	45	505	
98	3	88	14	19	16	17	86	83	81	505	81	20	11	90	73	28	69	72	31	30	505	44	42	49	53	50	46	47	60	58	56	505	
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

58	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505	62	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505	64	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505																
44	57	79	78	24	21	96	5	83	18	505	4	97	94	7	48	53	21	80	25	76	505	23	61	36	38	76	69	27	74	55	46	505	
42	59	22	23	77	80	6	95	16	85	505	98	3	8	93	59	42	79	22	75	26	505	78	40	65	63	25	32	66	35	45	56	505	
49	52	66	35	28	73	8	93	88	13	505	1	100	95	6	43	58	78	23	74	27	505	75	26	57	43	60	42	79	22	52	49	505	
53	48	39	62	69	32	94	7	86	15	505	99	2	5	96	51	50	24	77	28	73	505	34	67	44	58	41	59	30	71	51	50	505	
50	51	63	38	74	27	9	92	14	87	505	13	87	86	16	57	44	33	67	66	36	505	72	29	31	77	62	28	37	68	47	54	505	
46	55	36	65	26	75	89	12	81	20	505	88	14	15	85	41	60	68	34	35	65	505	21	80	70	24	39	73	64	33	53	48	505	
47	54	37	64	76	25	11	90	19	82	505	17	84	9	92	54	47	32	69	62	39	505	1	100	7	5	12	10	90	93	92	95	505	
60	41	68	33	71	30	91	10	17	84	505	83	18	91	10	55	46	70	31	40	61	505	98	3	94	96	89	91	11	8	9	6	505	
58	43	34	67	31	70	99	98	4	1	505	82	19	90	11	52	49	29	72	63	38	505	4	97	18	87	82	85	84	15	13	20	505	
56	45	61	40	29	72	2	3	97	100	505	20	81	12	89	45	56	71	30	37	64	505	99	2	83	14	19	16	17	86	88	81	505	
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

The complete list of 115 **striped magic squares** of order 10 is available at the author's web site: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=10587>.

5.1 Rotational Striped Magic Squares of Order 10

Below are few examples of **striped** magic squares of order 10 in **rotational forms**.

Example 5.1. Below are four **rotational forms** of **striped** magic squares of order 10 given in Example 25

25	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
13	88	93	8	68	33	69	23	38	72	505
18	83	95	6	40	61	32	78	63	29	505
85	16	5	96	30	71	54	47	22	79	505
87	14	7	94	44	57	48	53	58	43	505
84	17	90	11	80	21	49	52	59	42	505
20	81	10	91	34	67	46	55	74	27	505
82	19	92	9	73	28	56	45	60	41	505
15	86	12	89	35	66	50	51	36	65	505
1	99	98	4	77	62	37	26	25	76	505
100	2	3	97	24	39	64	75	70	31	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

26	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
98	99	1	4	68	33	69	23	38	72	505
3	2	100	97	40	61	32	78	63	29	505
93	8	13	88	30	71	54	47	22	79	505
95	6	18	83	44	57	48	53	58	43	505
5	96	84	17	80	21	49	52	59	42	505
7	94	87	14	35	66	46	55	74	27	505
90	11	85	16	73	28	56	45	60	41	505
12	89	20	81	34	67	50	51	36	65	505
10	91	82	19	77	62	37	26	25	76	505
92	9	15	86	24	39	64	75	70	31	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

27	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
44	57	69	23	38	72	98	99	1	4	505
40	61	32	78	63	29	3	2	100	97	505
30	71	54	47	22	79	92	9	82	19	505
68	33	49	52	58	43	95	6	18	83	505
80	21	48	53	59	42	5	96	85	16	505
34	67	46	55	74	27	7	94	15	86	505
73	28	56	45	60	41	90	11	84	17	505
35	66	50	51	36	65	10	91	20	81	505
77	62	37	26	25	76	93	8	13	88	505
24	39	64	75	70	31	12	89	87	14	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

28	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
44	57	69	23	38	72	13	88	93	8	505
35	66	32	78	63	29	18	83	95	6	505
30	71	56	45	22	79	85	16	5	96	505
68	33	49	52	58	43	87	14	7	94	505
80	21	48	53	59	42	15	86	90	11	505
34	67	46	55	74	27	20	81	10	91	505
73	28	54	47	60	41	84	17	92	9	505
40	61	50	51	36	65	82	19	12	89	505
77	62	37	26	25	76	98	99	1	4	505
24	39	64	75	70	31	3	2	100	97	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

Example 5.2. Below are four **rotational forms of striped** magic squares of order 10 given in Example 29.

29	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
13	88	93	8	45	55	47	51	52	53	505
87	14	92	9	56	46	54	50	49	48	505
15	86	12	89	21	80	29	71	70	32	505
85	16	7	94	79	22	72	30	31	69	505
84	17	90	11	74	27	37	63	62	40	505
18	83	10	91	23	78	64	38	39	61	505
82	19	95	6	77	24	36	65	41	60	505
20	81	5	96	26	75	33	68	58	43	505
1	99	4	98	76	25	67	34	59	42	505
100	2	97	3	28	73	66	35	44	57	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

30	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
1	99	4	98	45	55	47	51	52	53	505
100	2	97	3	56	46	54	50	49	48	505
13	88	92	9	21	80	29	71	70	32	505
87	14	93	8	79	22	72	30	31	69	505
15	86	12	89	74	27	37	63	62	40	505
84	17	7	94	23	78	64	38	39	61	505
20	81	90	11	77	24	66	35	41	60	505
18	83	95	6	26	75	33	68	58	43	505
82	19	10	91	76	25	36	65	59	42	505
85	16	5	96	28	73	67	34	44	57	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

31	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
87	14	93	8	21	80	67	34	58	43	505
13	88	92	9	79	22	36	65	59	42	505
15	86	12	89	28	73	33	68	44	57	505
85	16	7	94	77	24	66	35	41	60	505
84	17	95	6	26	75	37	63	62	40	505
18	83	10	91	74	27	64	38	39	61	505
82	19	90	11	76	25	32	70	29	71	505
20	81	5	96	23	78	69	31	72	30	505
1	4	99	98	55	53	47	51	52	45	505
100	97	2	3	46	48	54	50	49	56	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

32	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
4	1	99	98	21	80	66	35	59	42	505
97	100	2	3	79	22	36	65	58	43	505
13	88	95	6	28	73	33	68	44	57	505
87	14	5	96	77	24	67	34	41	60	505
15	86	12	89	26	75	37	63	62	40	505
85	16	7	94	74	27	64	38	39	61	505
20	81	93	8	76	25	32	70	29	71	505
18	83	10	91	23	78	69	31	72	30	505
82	19	90	11	55	53	47	51	45	52	505
84	17	92	9	46	48	54	50	56	49	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

Example 5.3. Below are four *rotational forms of striped* magic squares of order 10 given in Example 33.

33	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
13	88	93	8	53	52	47	51	45	55	505
87	14	92	9	48	49	54	50	56	46	505
15	86	10	91	70	71	29	32	23	78	505
85	16	5	96	31	30	72	69	21	80	505
84	17	90	11	62	40	63	37	76	25	505
18	83	12	89	39	61	38	64	79	22	505
82	19	95	6	41	60	67	34	77	24	505
20	81	7	94	58	43	66	35	26	75	505
1	98	4	99	59	42	36	65	74	27	505
100	3	97	2	44	57	33	68	28	73	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

34	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
1	99	4	98	52	53	47	51	45	55	505
100	2	97	3	49	48	54	50	56	46	505
82	19	93	8	70	71	29	32	23	78	505
87	14	95	6	31	30	72	69	21	80	505
15	86	12	89	62	40	63	37	76	25	505
84	17	7	94	39	61	38	64	79	22	505
18	83	90	11	41	60	66	35	77	24	505
85	16	92	9	58	43	36	65	28	73	505
13	88	10	91	59	42	67	34	74	27	505
20	81	5	96	44	57	33	68	26	75	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

35	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
13	88	93	8	41	60	36	65	23	78	505
87	14	92	9	58	43	33	68	28	73	505
15	86	10	91	59	42	67	34	74	27	505
85	16	5	96	44	57	66	35	79	22	505
84	17	95	6	63	40	62	37	77	24	505
18	83	7	94	38	61	39	64	26	75	505
82	19	90	11	32	71	70	29	76	25	505
20	81	12	89	69	30	31	72	21	80	505
1	98	4	99	45	53	55	51	52	47	505
100	3	97	2	56	48	46	50	49	54	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

36	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
1	98	4	99	41	60	67	34	28	73	505
100	3	97	2	58	43	33	68	21	80	505
82	19	93	8	59	42	36	65	74	27	505
87	14	12	89	44	57	66	35	79	22	505
15	86	95	6	63	40	62	37	77	24	505
84	17	7	94	38	61	39	64	26	75	505
13	88	92	9	29	32	70	71	76	25	505
85	16	90	11	72	69	31	30	23	78	505
18	83	10	91	45	52	55	51	47	53	505
20	81	5	96	56	49	46	50	54	48	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

Example 5.4. Below are four *rotational forms of striped* magic squares of order 10 given in Example 37.

37	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
13	88	93	8	52	55	47	51	45	53	505
87	14	92	9	49	46	54	50	56	48	505
15	86	12	89	23	78	36	65	41	60	505
85	16	7	94	79	22	67	34	58	43	505
84	17	95	6	74	27	33	68	59	42	505
18	83	5	96	21	80	66	35	44	57	505
82	19	90	11	77	24	37	63	62	40	505
20	81	10	91	26	75	64	38	39	61	505
4	98	1	99	76	25	70	32	71	29	505
97	3	100	2	28	73	31	69	30	72	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

38	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
4	98	1	99	45	55	47	52	51	53	505
97	3	100	2	56	46	54	49	50	48	505
13	88	93	8	21	80	36	65	41	60	505
87	14	92	9	79	22	67	34	58	43	505
15	86	12	89	74	27	33	68	59	42	505
85	16	7	94	23	78	66	35	44	57	505
84	17	10	91	77	24	40	37	62	63	505
18	83	90	11	26	75	61	64	39	38	505
82	19	95	6	76	25	29	70	71	32	505
20	81	5	96	28	73	72	31	30	69	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

39	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
98	4	99	1	21	80	71	70	29	32	505
3	97	2	100	79	22	30	31	72	69	505
13	88	90	11	28	73	37	63	62	40	505
87	14	95	6	77	24	64	38	39	61	505
15	86	10	91	26	75	66	35	59	42	505
20	81	7	94	74	27	36	65	58	43	505
84	17	92	9	76	25	33	68	44	57	505
18	83	12	89	23	78	67	34	41	60	505
82	19	93	8	55	53	47	51	45	52	505
85	16	5	96	46	48	54	50	56	49	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

40	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
87	14	93	8	21	80	71	29	70	32	505
13	88	92	9	79	22	30	72	31	69	505
15	86	12	89	28	73	62	40	63	37	505
85	16	7	94	77	24	39	61	38	64	505
84	17	95	6	26	75	66	35	59	42	505
18	83	10	91	74	27	36	65	58	43	505
82	19	90	11	76	25	33	68	44	57	505
20	81	5	96	23	78	67	34	41	60	505
1	98	4	99	45	53	47	51	55	52	505
100	3	97	2	56	48	54	50	46	49	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

Example 5.5. Below are four **rotational forms of striped** magic squares of order 10 given in Example 41.

41	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505
	1	98 4 99	45 55 47 52	51 53	505
	100	3 97 2	56 46 54 49	50 48	505
	13	88 93 8	41 60 36 65	76 25	505
	87	14 92 9	58 43 33 68	28 73	505
	15	86 10 91	59 42 67 34	74 27	505
	85	16 7 94	44 57 66 35	23 78	505
	84	17 12 89	37 62 63 40	77 24	505
	18	83 90 11	64 39 38 61	26 75	505
	82	19 95 6	29 71 70 32	79 22	505
	20	81 5 96	72 30 31 69	21 80	505
	505	505 505 505 505	505 505 505 505	505 505	505

42	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505
	20	81 93 8	52 53 47 51	45 55	505
	82	19 92 9	49 48 54 50	56 46	505
	15	86 5 96	44 57 36 65	21 80	505
	85	16 12 89	59 42 33 68	74 27	505
	84	17 90 11	58 43 67 34	76 25	505
	18	83 10 91	41 60 66 35	23 78	505
	13	88 95 6	37 40 63 62	77 24	505
	87	14 7 94	64 61 38 39	26 75	505
	1	99 4 98	29 71 70 32	79 22	505
	100	2 97 3	72 30 31 69	28 73	505
	505	505 505 505 505	505 505 505 505	505 505	505

43	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505
	4	1 98 99	29 71 70 32	28 73	505
	97	100 3 2	72 30 31 69	21 80	505
	13	88 93 8	62 40 63 37	74 27	505
	87	14 92 9	39 61 38 64	79 22	505
	15	86 10 91	41 60 67 34	77 24	505
	85	16 7 94	58 43 66 35	26 75	505
	84	17 12 89	59 42 36 65	76 25	505
	18	83 90 11	44 57 33 68	23 78	505
	82	19 95 6	53 52 47 51	55 45	505
	20	81 5 96	48 49 54 50	46 56	505
	505	505 505 505 505	505 505 505 505	505 505	505

44	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505
	20	81 93 8	29 71 70 32	23 78	505
	15	86 95 6	72 30 31 69	21 80	505
	85	16 12 89	62 40 63 37	74 27	505
	87	14 7 94	39 61 38 64	79 22	505
	84	17 90 11	41 60 36 65	77 24	505
	13	88 10 91	58 43 33 68	26 75	505
	82	19 92 9	59 42 67 34	76 25	505
	18	83 5 96	44 57 66 35	28 73	505
	1	99 98 4	45 52 55 51	53 47	505
	100	2 3 97	56 49 46 50	48 54	505
	505	505 505 505 505	505 505 505 505	505 505	505

Example 5.6. Below are four *rotational forms of striped* magic squares of order 10 given in Example 45.

45	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
21	79	28	77	26	74	76	23	55	46	505
80	22	73	24	75	27	25	78	45	56	505
66	36	33	67	37	64	32	69	47	54	505
35	65	68	34	63	38	70	31	51	50	505
59	58	44	41	62	29	39	72	53	48	505
42	43	57	60	40	71	61	30	52	49	505
1	100	5	96	9	92	13	88	82	19	505
4	97	8	93	91	10	16	85	17	84	505
98	3	94	7	90	11	86	15	83	18	505
99	2	95	6	12	89	87	14	20	81	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

45	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
55	46	29	72	62	39	41	44	59	58	505
45	56	32	69	40	61	60	57	42	43	505
52	49	71	30	63	38	36	33	67	66	505
51	50	70	31	37	64	65	68	34	35	505
53	48	23	21	74	76	77	26	79	28	505
47	54	78	80	27	25	24	75	22	73	505
1	100	94	7	9	92	13	88	20	81	505
4	97	95	6	91	10	87	14	83	18	505
98	3	5	96	90	11	86	15	82	19	505
99	2	8	93	12	89	16	85	17	84	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

45	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
28	79	21	77	26	74	76	23	55	46	505
73	22	80	24	75	27	25	78	51	50	505
66	36	33	67	37	64	32	69	47	54	505
35	65	68	34	63	38	70	31	53	48	505
59	58	44	41	62	39	29	72	45	56	505
42	43	57	60	40	61	71	30	52	49	505
98	3	8	93	9	92	87	14	17	84	505
4	97	94	7	91	10	86	15	83	18	505
99	2	5	96	90	11	13	88	82	19	505
1	100	95	6	12	89	16	85	20	81	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

45	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
45	56	28	76	74	23	77	26	79	21	505
55	46	73	25	27	78	24	75	22	80	505
47	54	70	31	37	64	36	33	67	66	505
51	50	71	30	63	38	65	68	34	35	505
52	49	29	72	62	39	41	58	59	44	505
53	48	32	69	40	61	60	43	42	57	505
98	3	8	93	9	92	13	88	17	84	505
99	2	94	7	91	10	87	14	82	19	505
4	97	5	96	90	11	86	15	83	18	505
1	100	95	6	12	89	16	85	20	81	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

45	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
98	4	99	1	80	21	68	33	69	32	505
3	97	2	100	22	79	34	67	31	70	505
8	94	5	95	78	23	65	36	72	29	505
93	7	96	6	75	26	35	66	30	71	505
9	91	90	12	25	76	40	62	63	37	505
92	10	11	89	24	77	61	39	38	64	505
87	86	13	16	27	74	44	41	58	59	505
14	15	88	85	73	28	57	60	43	42	505
17	83	82	20	53	45	51	52	47	55	505
84	18	19	81	48	56	50	49	54	46	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

45	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
21	80	66	35	59	42	1	4	98	99	505
79	22	36	65	58	43	100	97	3	2	505
28	73	33	68	44	57	5	8	94	95	505
77	24	67	34	41	60	96	93	7	6	505
26	75	37	63	62	40	9	91	90	12	505
74	27	64	38	29	71	92	10	11	89	505
76	25	32	70	39	61	13	16	86	87	505
23	78	69	31	72	30	88	85	15	14	505
55	45	47	51	53	52	82	17	83	20	505
46	56	54	50	48	49	19	84	18	81	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

45	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
98	4	99	1	46	54	50	49	48	56	505
3	97	2	100	55	47	51	52	53	45	505
8	95	5	94	73	28	57	42	43	60	505
93	6	96	7	27	74	44	59	58	41	505
9	91	90	12	24	77	61	39	38	64	505
92	10	11	89	25	76	40	62	63	37	505
87	86	13	16	75	26	65	36	69	32	505
14	15	88	85	78	23	68	33	72	29	505
17	20	82	83	22	79	34	67	30	71	505
84	81	19	18	80	21	35	66	31	70	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

45	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
55	45	52	51	53	47	1	4	98	99	505
46	56	49	50	48	54	100	97	3	2	505
29	32	71	70	23	78	94	95	5	8	505
72	69	30	31	21	80	7	6	96	93	505
62	40	63	37	74	27	9	91	90	12	505
39	61	38	64	76	25	92	10	11	89	505
41	60	36	65	77	24	13	87	86	16	505
44	57	33	68	26	75	88	14	15	85	505
59	42	67	34	79	22	20	83	82	17	505
58	43	66	35	28	73	81	18	19	84	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

Example 5.7. Below are four *rotational forms of striped* magic squares of order 10 given in Example 49.

49	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
45	56	41	58	59	44	62	39	71	30	505
55	46	60	43	42	57	40	61	70	31	505
47	54	33	67	36	66	63	38	29	72	505
51	50	68	34	65	35	37	64	32	69	505
52	49	21	74	79	23	77	26	76	28	505
53	48	80	27	22	78	24	75	25	73	505
98	3	8	93	9	92	13	88	17	84	505
99	2	94	7	91	10	87	14	83	18	505
4	97	5	96	90	11	86	15	82	19	505
1	100	95	6	12	89	16	85	20	81	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

49	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
29	72	62	39	41	58	59	44	51	50	505
71	30	63	38	60	43	42	57	45	56	505
70	31	40	61	36	66	67	33	55	46	505
32	69	37	64	65	35	34	68	52	49	505
23	21	74	79	77	26	76	28	53	48	505
78	80	27	22	24	75	25	73	47	54	505
1	100	5	96	9	92	13	88	17	84	505
4	97	95	6	91	10	87	14	83	18	505
98	3	94	7	90	11	86	15	82	19	505
99	2	8	93	12	89	16	85	20	81	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

49	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
21	79	28	77	26	74	76	23	45	56	505
80	22	73	24	75	27	25	78	55	46	505
32	69	37	64	66	67	33	36	47	54	505
70	31	40	61	35	34	68	65	51	50	505
29	72	62	39	59	58	44	41	53	48	505
71	30	63	38	42	43	57	60	52	49	505
98	3	8	93	9	92	13	88	17	84	505
4	97	94	7	91	10	16	85	82	19	505
99	2	5	96	90	11	86	15	83	18	505
1	100	95	6	12	89	87	14	20	81	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

49	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
45	56	21	79	74	23	77	26	76	28	505
55	46	80	22	27	78	24	75	25	73	505
47	54	36	33	67	66	62	39	29	72	505
51	50	65	68	34	35	37	64	71	30	505
52	49	44	58	59	41	63	38	70	31	505
53	48	57	43	42	60	40	61	32	69	505
1	100	5	96	9	92	13	88	17	84	505
4	97	95	6	91	10	87	14	82	19	505
98	3	94	7	90	11	86	15	83	18	505
99	2	8	93	12	89	16	85	20	81	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

Example 5.8. Below are four **rotational forms of striped** magic squares of order 10 given in Example 53.

53	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
48	53	63	38	58	43	78	23	71	30	505
56	45	40	61	41	60	24	77	70	31	505
49	52	37	64	59	42	79	22	29	72	505
50	51	62	39	44	57	21	80	32	69	505
54	47	65	34	68	35	25	75	74	28	505
46	55	36	67	33	66	76	26	27	73	505
1	100	7	5	12	10	95	93	92	90	505
99	2	94	96	89	91	6	8	9	11	505
4	97	13	87	82	85	84	15	18	20	505
98	3	88	14	19	16	17	86	83	81	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

53	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
30	71	23	78	43	58	38	63	53	48	505
31	70	77	24	60	41	61	40	45	56	505
72	29	22	79	42	59	64	37	52	49	505
69	32	80	21	57	44	39	62	51	50	505
28	74	75	25	35	68	34	65	47	54	505
73	27	26	76	66	33	67	36	55	46	505
90	92	93	95	10	12	5	7	100	1	505
11	9	8	6	91	89	96	94	2	99	505
20	18	15	84	85	82	87	13	97	4	505
81	83	86	17	16	19	14	88	3	98	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

53	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
98	3	88	14	19	16	17	86	83	81	505
4	97	13	87	82	85	84	15	18	20	505
99	2	94	96	89	91	6	8	9	11	505
1	100	7	5	12	10	95	93	92	90	505
46	55	36	67	33	66	76	26	27	73	505
54	47	65	34	68	35	25	75	74	28	505
50	51	62	39	44	57	21	80	32	69	505
49	52	37	64	59	42	79	22	29	72	505
56	45	40	61	41	60	24	77	70	31	505
48	53	63	38	58	43	78	23	71	30	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

53	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
81	83	86	17	16	19	14	88	3	98	505
20	18	15	84	85	82	87	13	97	4	505
11	9	8	6	91	89	96	94	2	99	505
90	92	93	95	10	12	5	7	100	1	505
73	27	26	76	66	33	67	36	55	46	505
28	74	75	25	35	68	34	65	47	54	505
69	32	80	21	57	44	39	62	51	50	505
72	29	22	79	42	59	64	37	52	49	505
31	70	77	24	60	41	61	40	45	56	505
30	71	23	78	43	58	38	63	53	48	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

Example 5.9. Below are four *rotational forms of striped* magic squares of order 10 given in Example 55.

55	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/								©IJT	505
	98	4	99	1	46	54	50	49	56	48	505
	3	97	2	100	55	47	51	52	45	53	505
	88	13	94	7	36	65	62	37	40	63	505
	14	87	96	5	67	34	39	64	61	38	505
	19	82	89	12	33	68	44	59	41	58	505
	16	85	91	10	66	35	57	42	60	43	505
	17	84	6	95	76	25	21	79	24	78	505
	86	15	8	93	26	75	80	22	77	23	505
	83	18	9	92	27	74	32	29	70	71	505
	81	20	11	90	73	28	69	72	31	30	505
	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

55	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/								©IJT	505
	48	56	49	50	54	46	1	99	4	98	505
	53	45	52	51	47	55	100	2	97	3	505
	63	40	37	62	65	36	7	94	13	88	505
	38	61	64	39	34	67	5	96	87	14	505
	58	41	59	44	68	33	12	89	82	19	505
	43	60	42	57	35	66	10	91	85	16	505
	78	24	79	21	25	76	95	6	84	17	505
	23	77	22	80	75	26	93	8	15	86	505
	71	70	29	32	74	27	92	9	18	83	505
	30	31	72	69	28	73	90	11	20	81	505
	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

55	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/								©IJT	505
	81	20	11	90	73	28	69	72	31	30	505
	83	18	9	92	27	74	32	29	70	71	505
	86	15	8	93	26	75	80	22	77	23	505
	17	84	6	95	76	25	21	79	24	78	505
	16	85	91	10	66	35	57	42	60	43	505
	19	82	89	12	33	68	44	59	41	58	505
	14	87	96	5	67	34	39	64	61	38	505
	88	13	94	7	36	65	62	37	40	63	505
	3	97	2	100	55	47	51	52	45	53	505
	98	4	99	1	46	54	50	49	56	48	505
	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

55	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/								©IJT	505
	30	31	72	69	28	73	90	11	20	81	505
	71	70	29	32	74	27	92	9	18	83	505
	23	77	22	80	75	26	93	8	15	86	505
	78	24	79	21	25	76	95	6	84	17	505
	43	60	42	57	35	66	10	91	85	16	505
	58	41	59	44	68	33	12	89	82	19	505
	38	61	64	39	34	67	5	96	87	14	505
	63	40	37	62	65	36	7	94	13	88	505
	53	45	52	51	47	55	100	2	97	3	505
	48	56	49	50	54	46	1	99	4	98	505
	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

Example 5.10. Below are four *rotational forms* of *striped* magic squares of order 10 given in Example 57.

57	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
18	85	13	15	87	20	82	84	1	100	505
83	16	88	86	14	81	19	17	4	97	505
5	95	93	7	92	12	90	10	98	3	505
96	6	8	94	9	89	11	91	99	2	505
21	80	73	32	27	75	25	30	70	72	505
24	77	28	69	74	26	76	71	31	29	505
78	23	35	62	38	65	64	33	67	40	505
79	22	66	39	63	36	37	68	34	61	505
57	59	52	48	51	55	54	41	43	45	505
44	42	49	53	50	46	47	60	58	56	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

57	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
100	1	84	82	20	87	15	13	85	18	505
97	4	17	19	81	14	86	88	16	83	505
3	98	10	90	12	92	7	93	95	5	505
2	99	91	11	89	9	94	8	6	96	505
72	70	30	25	75	27	32	73	80	21	505
29	31	71	76	26	74	69	28	77	24	505
40	67	33	64	65	38	62	35	23	78	505
61	34	68	37	36	63	39	66	22	79	505
45	43	41	54	55	51	48	52	59	57	505
56	58	60	47	46	50	53	49	42	44	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

57	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
56	58	60	47	46	50	53	49	42	44	505
45	43	41	54	55	51	48	52	59	57	505
61	34	68	37	36	63	39	66	22	79	505
40	67	33	64	65	38	62	35	23	78	505
29	31	71	76	26	74	69	28	77	24	505
72	70	30	25	75	27	32	73	80	21	505
2	99	91	11	89	9	94	8	6	96	505
3	98	10	90	12	92	7	93	95	5	505
97	4	17	19	81	14	86	88	16	83	505
100	1	84	82	20	87	15	13	85	18	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

57	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
44	42	49	53	50	46	47	60	58	56	505
57	59	52	48	51	55	54	41	43	45	505
79	22	66	39	63	36	37	68	34	61	505
78	23	35	62	38	65	64	33	67	40	505
24	77	28	69	74	26	76	71	31	29	505
21	80	73	32	27	75	25	30	70	72	505
96	6	8	94	9	89	11	91	99	2	505
5	95	93	7	92	12	90	10	98	3	505
83	16	88	86	14	81	19	17	4	97	505
18	85	13	15	87	20	82	84	1	100	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

Example 5.11. Below are four *rotational forms of striped* magic squares of order 10 given in Example 58.

58	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
44	57	79	78	24	21	96	5	83	18	505
42	59	22	23	77	80	6	95	16	85	505
49	52	66	35	28	73	8	93	88	13	505
53	48	39	62	69	32	94	7	86	15	505
50	51	63	38	74	27	9	92	14	87	505
46	55	36	65	26	75	89	12	81	20	505
47	54	37	64	76	25	11	90	19	82	505
60	41	68	33	71	30	91	10	17	84	505
58	43	34	67	31	70	99	98	4	1	505
56	45	61	40	29	72	2	3	97	100	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

58	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
18	83	5	96	21	24	78	79	57	44	505
85	16	95	6	80	77	23	22	59	42	505
13	88	93	8	73	28	35	66	52	49	505
15	86	7	94	32	69	62	39	48	53	505
87	14	92	9	27	74	38	63	51	50	505
20	81	12	89	75	26	65	36	55	46	505
82	19	90	11	25	76	64	37	54	47	505
84	17	10	91	30	71	33	68	41	60	505
1	4	98	99	70	31	67	34	43	58	505
100	97	3	2	72	29	40	61	45	56	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

58	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
100	97	3	2	72	29	40	61	45	56	505
1	4	98	99	70	31	67	34	43	58	505
84	17	10	91	30	71	33	68	41	60	505
82	19	90	11	25	76	64	37	54	47	505
20	81	12	89	75	26	65	36	55	46	505
87	14	92	9	27	74	38	63	51	50	505
15	86	7	94	32	69	62	39	48	53	505
13	88	93	8	73	28	35	66	52	49	505
85	16	95	6	80	77	23	22	59	42	505
18	83	5	96	21	24	78	79	57	44	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

58	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
56	45	61	40	29	72	2	3	97	100	505
58	43	34	67	31	70	99	98	4	1	505
60	41	68	33	71	30	91	10	17	84	505
47	54	37	64	76	25	11	90	19	82	505
46	55	36	65	26	75	89	12	81	20	505
50	51	63	38	74	27	9	92	14	87	505
53	48	39	62	69	32	94	7	86	15	505
49	52	66	35	28	73	8	93	88	13	505
42	59	22	23	77	80	6	95	16	85	505
44	57	79	78	24	21	96	5	83	18	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

Example 5.12. Below are four *rotational forms of striped* magic squares of order 10 given in Example 64.

64	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
80	81	24	86	95	8	3	27	25	76	505
21	20	77	15	6	93	98	74	11	90	505
14	87	37	64	29	72	33	68	92	9	505
94	7	63	38	71	30	66	35	75	26	505
12	89	62	39	70	31	67	34	17	84	505
4	97	40	61	32	69	36	65	83	18	505
100	1	85	88	28	91	5	2	23	82	505
79	22	16	13	73	10	96	99	78	19	505
43	59	48	51	45	57	54	52	41	55	505
58	42	53	50	56	44	47	49	60	46	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

65	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
46	60	49	47	44	56	50	53	42	58	505
55	41	52	54	57	45	51	48	59	43	505
19	78	99	96	10	73	13	16	22	79	505
82	23	2	5	91	28	88	85	1	100	505
18	83	65	36	69	32	61	40	97	4	505
84	17	34	67	31	70	39	62	89	12	505
26	75	35	66	30	71	38	63	7	94	505
9	92	68	33	72	29	64	37	87	14	505
90	11	74	98	93	6	15	77	20	21	505
76	25	27	3	8	95	86	24	81	80	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

66	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
58	43	79	100	4	12	94	14	21	80	505
42	59	22	1	97	89	7	87	20	81	505
53	48	16	85	40	62	63	37	77	24	505
50	51	13	88	61	39	38	64	15	86	505
56	45	73	28	32	70	71	29	6	95	505
44	57	10	91	69	31	30	72	93	8	505
47	54	96	5	36	67	66	33	98	3	505
49	52	99	2	65	34	35	68	74	27	505
60	41	78	23	83	17	75	92	11	25	505
46	55	19	82	18	84	26	9	90	76	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

67	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
76	90	9	26	84	18	82	19	55	46	505
25	11	92	75	17	83	23	78	41	60	505
27	74	68	35	34	65	2	99	52	49	505
3	98	33	66	67	36	5	96	54	47	505
8	93	72	30	31	69	91	10	57	44	505
95	6	29	71	70	32	28	73	45	56	505
86	15	64	38	39	61	88	13	51	50	505
24	77	37	63	62	40	85	16	48	53	505
81	20	87	7	89	97	1	22	59	42	505
80	21	14	94	12	4	100	79	43	58	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

Example 5.13. Below are four *rotational forms of striped* magic squares of order 10 given in Example 100.

100	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
95	8	83	12	86	19	81	20	67	34	505
6	93	18	89	15	82	9	92	33	68	505
10	91	79	24	78	21	96	5	35	66	505
17	84	22	77	23	80	16	85	65	36	505
88	13	3	100	7	99	90	4	64	37	505
87	14	98	1	94	2	11	97	38	63	505
75	27	32	72	70	30	25	73	62	39	505
26	74	69	29	31	71	76	28	40	61	505
59	41	43	51	48	45	54	52	55	57	505
42	60	58	50	53	56	47	49	46	44	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

100	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
34	67	20	81	19	86	12	83	8	95	505
68	33	92	9	82	15	89	18	93	6	505
66	35	5	96	21	78	24	79	91	10	505
36	65	85	16	80	23	77	22	84	17	505
37	64	4	90	99	7	100	3	13	88	505
63	38	97	11	2	94	1	98	14	87	505
39	62	73	25	30	70	72	32	27	75	505
61	40	28	76	71	31	29	69	74	26	505
57	55	52	54	45	48	51	43	41	59	505
44	46	49	47	56	53	50	58	60	42	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

100	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
44	46	49	47	56	53	50	58	60	42	505
57	55	52	54	45	48	51	43	41	59	505
61	40	28	76	71	31	29	69	74	26	505
39	62	73	25	30	70	72	32	27	75	505
63	38	97	11	2	94	1	98	14	87	505
37	64	4	90	99	7	100	3	13	88	505
36	65	85	16	80	23	77	22	84	17	505
66	35	5	96	21	78	24	79	91	10	505
68	33	92	9	82	15	89	18	93	6	505
34	67	20	81	19	86	12	83	8	95	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

100	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
42	60	58	50	53	56	47	49	46	44	505
59	41	43	51	48	45	54	52	55	57	505
26	74	69	29	31	71	76	28	40	61	505
75	27	32	72	70	30	25	73	62	39	505
87	14	98	1	94	2	11	97	38	63	505
88	13	3	100	7	99	90	4	64	37	505
17	84	22	77	23	80	16	85	65	36	505
10	91	79	24	78	21	96	5	35	66	505
6	93	18	89	15	82	9	92	33	68	505
95	8	83	12	86	19	81	20	67	34	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

100	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
42	59	26	75	87	88	17	10	6	95	505
60	41	74	27	14	13	84	91	93	8	505
58	43	69	32	98	3	22	79	18	83	505
50	51	29	72	1	100	77	24	89	12	505
53	48	31	70	94	7	23	78	15	86	505
56	45	71	30	2	99	80	21	82	19	505
47	54	76	25	11	90	16	96	9	81	505
49	52	28	73	97	4	85	5	92	20	505
46	55	40	62	38	64	65	35	33	67	505
44	57	61	39	63	37	36	66	68	34	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

100	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
95	6	10	17	88	87	75	26	59	42	505
8	93	91	84	13	14	27	74	41	60	505
83	18	79	22	3	98	32	69	43	58	505
12	89	24	77	100	1	72	29	51	50	505
86	15	78	23	7	94	70	31	48	53	505
19	82	21	80	99	2	30	71	45	56	505
81	9	96	16	90	11	25	76	54	47	505
20	92	5	85	4	97	73	28	52	49	505
67	33	35	65	64	38	62	40	55	46	505
34	68	66	36	37	63	39	61	57	44	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

100	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
34	68	66	36	37	63	39	61	57	44	505
67	33	35	65	64	38	62	40	55	46	505
20	92	5	85	4	97	73	28	52	49	505
81	9	96	16	90	11	25	76	54	47	505
19	82	21	80	99	2	30	71	45	56	505
86	15	78	23	7	94	70	31	48	53	505
12	89	24	77	100	1	72	29	51	50	505
83	18	79	22	3	98	32	69	43	58	505
8	93	91	84	13	14	27	74	41	60	505
95	6	10	17	88	87	75	26	59	42	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

100	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
44	57	61	39	63	37	36	66	68	34	505
46	55	40	62	38	64	65	35	33	67	505
49	52	28	73	97	4	85	5	92	20	505
47	54	76	25	11	90	16	96	9	81	505
56	45	71	30	2	99	80	21	82	19	505
53	48	31	70	94	7	23	78	15	86	505
50	51	29	72	1	100	77	24	89	12	505
58	43	69	32	98	3	22	79	18	83	505
60	41	74	27	14	13	84	91	93	8	505
42	59	26	75	87	88	17	10	6	95	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

Example 5.14. Below are four *rotational forms of striped* magic squares of order 10 given in Example 104.

104	mgc											505
	23	78	86	15	20	81	12	89	38	63	505	
	77	24	16	85	82	19	90	11	64	37	505	
	22	79	87	14	83	18	91	10	35	66	505	
	80	21	13	88	17	84	9	92	67	34	505	
	3	1	99	97	96	94	6	8	65	36	505	
	98	100	2	4	5	7	95	93	33	68	505	
	73	27	30	72	75	25	32	70	62	39	505	
	28	74	71	29	26	76	69	31	40	61	505	
	43	59	52	51	48	45	54	55	57	41	505	
	58	42	49	50	53	56	47	46	44	60	505	
	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	

104	mgc											505
	60	44	46	47	56	53	50	49	42	58	505	
	41	57	55	54	45	48	51	52	59	43	505	
	61	40	31	69	76	26	29	71	74	28	505	
	39	62	70	32	25	75	72	30	27	73	505	
	68	33	93	95	7	5	4	2	100	98	505	
	36	65	8	6	94	96	97	99	1	3	505	
	34	67	92	9	84	17	88	13	21	80	505	
	66	35	10	91	18	83	14	87	79	22	505	
	37	64	11	90	19	82	85	16	24	77	505	
	63	38	89	12	81	20	15	86	78	23	505	
	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	

104	mgc											505
	58	43	28	73	98	3	15	85	14	88	505	
	42	59	74	27	100	1	86	16	87	13	505	
	49	52	71	30	2	99	78	24	79	21	505	
	50	51	29	72	4	97	23	77	22	80	505	
	53	48	26	75	5	96	17	83	82	20	505	
	56	45	76	25	7	94	84	18	19	81	505	
	47	54	69	32	95	6	9	91	90	12	505	
	46	55	31	70	93	8	92	10	11	89	505	
	44	57	40	62	33	65	67	35	64	38	505	
	60	41	61	39	68	36	34	66	37	63	505	
	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	

104	mgc											505
	63	37	66	34	36	68	39	61	41	60	505	
	38	64	35	67	65	33	62	40	57	44	505	
	89	11	10	92	8	93	70	31	55	46	505	
	12	90	91	9	6	95	32	69	54	47	505	
	81	19	18	84	94	7	25	76	45	56	505	
	20	82	83	17	96	5	75	26	48	53	505	
	80	22	77	23	97	4	72	29	51	50	505	
	21	79	24	78	99	2	30	71	52	49	505	
	13	87	16	86	1	100	27	74	59	42	505	
	88	14	85	15	3	98	73	28	43	58	505	
	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	

Example 5.15. Below are four *rotational forms of striped* magic squares of order 10 given in Example 108.

108	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
23	77	22	80	20	81	12	89	38	63	505
78	24	79	21	82	19	90	11	64	37	505
86	16	87	13	83	18	91	10	35	66	505
15	85	14	88	17	84	9	92	67	34	505
3	1	99	97	96	94	6	8	65	36	505
98	100	2	4	5	7	95	93	33	68	505
73	27	30	72	75	25	32	70	62	39	505
28	74	71	29	26	76	69	31	40	61	505
43	59	52	51	48	45	54	55	57	41	505
58	42	49	50	53	56	47	46	44	60	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

108	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
63	38	89	12	81	20	80	22	77	23	505
37	64	11	90	19	82	21	79	24	78	505
66	35	10	91	18	83	13	87	16	86	505
34	67	92	9	84	17	88	14	85	15	505
36	65	8	6	94	96	97	99	1	3	505
68	33	93	95	7	5	4	2	100	98	505
39	62	70	32	25	75	72	30	27	73	505
61	40	31	69	76	26	29	71	74	28	505
41	57	55	54	45	48	51	52	59	43	505
60	44	46	47	56	53	50	49	42	58	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

108	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
60	44	46	47	56	53	50	49	42	58	505
41	57	55	54	45	48	51	52	59	43	505
61	40	31	69	76	26	29	71	74	28	505
39	62	70	32	25	75	72	30	27	73	505
68	33	93	95	7	5	4	2	100	98	505
36	65	8	6	94	96	97	99	1	3	505
34	67	92	9	84	17	88	14	85	15	505
66	35	10	91	18	83	13	87	16	86	505
37	64	11	90	19	82	21	79	24	78	505
63	38	89	12	81	20	80	22	77	23	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

108	mgc	10x10	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	505					
58	42	49	50	53	56	47	46	44	60	505
43	59	52	51	48	45	54	55	57	41	505
28	74	71	29	26	76	69	31	40	61	505
73	27	30	72	75	25	32	70	62	39	505
98	100	2	4	5	7	95	93	33	68	505
3	1	99	97	96	94	6	8	65	36	505
15	85	14	88	17	84	9	92	67	34	505
86	16	87	13	83	18	91	10	35	66	505
78	24	79	21	82	19	90	11	64	37	505
23	77	22	80	20	81	12	89	38	63	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

108	mgc	10x10		https://numbers-magic.com/		©IJT		505		
58	43	28	73	98	3	15	86	78	23	505
42	59	74	27	100	1	85	16	24	77	505
49	52	71	30	2	99	14	87	79	22	505
50	51	29	72	4	97	88	13	21	80	505
53	48	26	75	5	96	17	83	82	20	505
56	45	76	25	7	94	84	18	19	81	505
47	54	69	32	95	6	9	91	90	12	505
46	55	31	70	93	8	92	10	11	89	505
44	57	40	62	33	65	67	35	64	38	505
60	41	61	39	68	36	34	66	37	63	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

108	mgc	10x10		https://numbers-magic.com/		©IJT		505		
23	78	86	15	3	98	73	28	43	58	505
77	24	16	85	1	100	27	74	59	42	505
22	79	87	14	99	2	30	71	52	49	505
80	21	13	88	97	4	72	29	51	50	505
20	82	83	17	96	5	75	26	48	53	505
81	19	18	84	94	7	25	76	45	56	505
12	90	91	9	6	95	32	69	54	47	505
89	11	10	92	8	93	70	31	55	46	505
38	64	35	67	65	33	62	40	57	44	505
63	37	66	34	36	68	39	61	41	60	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

108	mgc	10x10		https://numbers-magic.com/		©IJT		505		
23	78	86	15	3	98	73	28	43	58	505
77	24	16	85	1	100	27	74	59	42	505
22	79	87	14	99	2	30	71	52	49	505
80	21	13	88	97	4	72	29	51	50	505
20	82	83	17	96	5	75	26	48	53	505
81	19	18	84	94	7	25	76	45	56	505
12	90	91	9	6	95	32	69	54	47	505
89	11	10	92	8	93	70	31	55	46	505
38	64	35	67	65	33	62	40	57	44	505
63	37	66	34	36	68	39	61	41	60	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

108	mgc	10x10		https://numbers-magic.com/		©IJT		505		
60	41	61	39	68	36	34	66	37	63	505
44	57	40	62	33	65	67	35	64	38	505
46	55	31	70	93	8	92	10	11	89	505
47	54	69	32	95	6	9	91	90	12	505
56	45	76	25	7	94	84	18	19	81	505
53	48	26	75	5	96	17	83	82	20	505
50	51	29	72	4	97	88	13	21	80	505
49	52	71	30	2	99	14	87	79	22	505
42	59	74	27	100	1	85	16	24	77	505
58	43	28	73	98	3	15	86	78	23	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

6 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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